

SYNTHESIS OF DRUG LOADED IRON OXIDE NANOPARTICLES

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SUMMARY

Sonochemically synthesized iron oxide and PVA-coated iron oxide nanoparticles were loaded with cancer therapy drugs and tested for their drug loading capacity and retention of magnetic properties. Polymer coatings such as polyvinyl alcohol have been developed to provide both biocompatibility and an environment for drug loading. The transmission electron microscopic and magnetic characterizations show that the magnetic particles are ~10nm in size and superparamagnetic in nature.

Keywords: *Sonochemical, Oleic acid, Pluronic-127, magnetite*

INTRODUCTION

The need to improved drug efficiency for both patient convenience and effective therapeutic uses has led to various areas of research including the development of magnetic carrier systems for drug delivery applications. Many drugs, particularly those associated with cancer therapy cannot be used effectively without the added complications of non-specific toxicities and severe side effects resulting from an attack on healthy cells. It is therefore assumed that a more effective method of delivery is that in which the majority of the drug is not released until the specified destination has been reached. In addition to reducing the side effects, the required dosage can be reduced since the amount reaching the targeted site will increase. Among the possible delivery vehicles are magnetic carrying devices which involve the use of drug loaded magnetic nanoparticles that are transported through the bloodstream to the targeted site by an external magnetic field. These carriers may be composed of any material that is magnetic and bio-compatible as synthesized or through additional coatings. Unlike bulk magnetic materials, the potential of their nanoparticles as drug carriers is made possible through their size compatibility with cells, viruses, and genes [1] in addition to the superparamagnetic properties which allow them to maintain magnetization only in the presence of a magnetic field.

Superparamagnetism is a unique phenomenon exhibited in some nano size materials that would otherwise show paramagnetic behavior above a critical size. According the Langevin theory [2] where a is magnetic saturation (Eq. 1), μ is magnetic moment, H is field strength, κ is Boltzman constant, and T is temperature, paramagnetic materials will only reach saturation if either the field is high or the temperature is low enough.

$$a = \frac{\mu H}{\kappa T} \quad [1]$$

Typically, in paramagnetics, room temperature is high enough to cause thermal agitations that increase the randomness of the magnetic moment and reduce the susceptibility. Nano-size superparamagnetics can act as single-domains and are therefore small enough to overcome energy barriers that would prevent alignment in the direction of the field at room temperature. As a result, SPMs have an increased susceptibility and do not require very high magnetic fields or low temperatures to reach saturation. Because these materials require the presence of a field to align their magnetic moments and magnetize, they lose most or all of their magnetization once the field is removed.

Magnetic nanoparticles can be synthesized through various methods including solution precipitation, thermal decomposition, sonochemical, and microwave heating [3-6]. The materials reported in this paper were synthesized using sonochemical technique. Sonochemistry [7-9] arises from acoustic cavitation phenomenon. During sonication, ultrasound waves create cavitations that form, grow, and burst, producing high temperature and pressure points that provide the ideal environment for chemical reactions. Mostly nanosized materials are produced from this method due to the rapid cooling after the bursting of the bubble. The conditions of the bubble have been reported to reach temperatures of $\sim 5000^\circ\text{C}$, pressures of ~ 1000 atm, and cooling rates above 10^{10} K/s. The primary precursor used is typically a volatile material since the reactions occur in the gas phase. Using these extreme conditions, Suslick and co-workers have prepared amorphous iron by the sonochemical decomposition of metal carbonyls in an alkane solvent [10]. We have also synthesized various magnetic nanomaterials from metal acetates and metal carbonyls [11-13].

In addition to magnetic requirements, drug carrying systems must meet minimum biocompatibility requirements. Foreign materials that enter the body can induce an immediate response from the immune system to remove it from the body. Additional steps are required to reduce premature metabolism, immunological reactions, rapid excretion and specific and non specific toxicities of the material. One common method to increase the biocompatibility is to coat the particles with a biocompatible material. Several polymers such as Oleic acid [14-15], Pluronic-127 [16], PVA (polyvinyl alcohol) [17], PLGA (poly(D,L-lactide-co-glycolide)) [18], and poly(ethyl-2-cyanoacrylate) [19] have been used. As well as increasing the compatibility, polymer coatings can serve to increase the hydrophilic nature of the particles in addition to providing an environment for drug loading.

The goal of this project is to produce magnetic nanoparticles that can be loaded with cancer therapy drugs such as Doxorubicin [20] and Taxol [21] and directed to the desired site with an external magnetic field. The requirements of such a system include size restrictions, minimum magnetization properties, and biocompatibility. In this manuscript we are reporting the synthesis and characterization of PVA-coated iron oxide nanoparticles from sonochemical techniques and Pluronic-127/oleic acid coated iron oxide particles coated post synthesis. All iron nanoparticles were synthesized using sonochemical techniques.

EXPERIMENTATION

Materials

All starting materials including iron pentacarbonyl ($\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$), Decalin, PEG (Polyethylene Glycol), and PVA was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA.

Synthesis of Fe_3O_4

Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were synthesized through ultrasonic irradiation of a solution of iron pentacarbonyl (2mL), Decalin (40 mL), and PEG (20mL) for 3 hours at 50% power using a high intensity ultrasonic horn (Ti-horn, 20kHz, 100W/cm²). The reaction was carried out in open air in a stainless steel vessel. The reaction vessel temperature was maintained at $\sim 30^\circ\text{C}$ by circulating the water using a thermostat. The solution was diluted in ethanol and centrifuged (Allegra 64R centrifuge) at 15, 000 rpm at 5°C . The precipitate was washed several times with water followed by ethanol and dried overnight under vacuum. The dried sample was heated to 300°C at a rate of 20/min for 3hrs under a steady flow of Argon. The as prepared sample was analyzed using XRD, TEM, and magnetic studies.

Synthesis of PVA coated Fe_3O_4

PVA-coated nanoparticles were synthesized using a similar synthesis procedure as the uncoated Fe_3O_4 except the addition of PVA. The detailed experimental procedure is as follows: PVA (0.56g) was added to the PEG (20mL) and mixed with the mixture of iron pentacarbonyl and decalin. The solution was irradiated with ultrasound waves for 3 hrs in open air at 30°C . The solution was centrifuged and washes several times with ethanol and dried overnight under vacuum. The as-prepared sample is divided in to two half's and first half is heated for 24 hrs at 200°C (PVA-coated200). The other half of is heated at 300°C for 3hrs sample (PVA-coated300). The samples were analyzed using XRD, TEM, and magnetometry.

Oleic acid coating

Uncoated Fe_3O_4 particles were coated with oleic acid, followed by a second layer of Pluronic-127. To coat the particles with oleic acid, the Fe_3O_4 particles were dispersed in 150 mL of distilled water and the pH was increased to 8-10 using 2M KOH. Oleic acid (2mL) was added to the alkaline solution and stirred for 30 minutes at 80°C . Upon cooling to room temperature, the particles were collected by placing a magnet on the outside of the beaker and leaving overnight. The separated particles were washed with distilled water until there was no remaining oily residue.

Pluronic-127 coating

The oleic-acid coated particles were dispersed in 45mL of distilled water and 100 mg of Pluronic-27 was added to the mixture. The reaction mixture was sonicated in a water bath for ~ 5 minutes and stirred over night at room temperature to disperse the aggregated Fe_3O_4 particles. The Pluronic-127/oleic acid coated particles were collected using a magnet. The product was washed with distilled water and dried overnight under vacuum. The samples were characterized using FTIR and TGA.

RESULTS

X-Ray diffraction

X-ray diffraction of as-synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles was conducted to determine the crystal structure and crystalline nature of the particles. Since as-prepared materials are amorphous in nature the X-ray diffraction patterns of as-prepared materials heated at 200°C and 300°C are shown in Figure 1. The powder X-ray diffraction pattern of Figure 1(a) clearly shows the uncoated iron oxide is highly crystalline and all the peaks are assigned to the magnetite JCPDS file number 19-0629. No impurities were observed in this sample. The widening of the diffraction peaks are assigned to the nature of the nanosized particles. Figure 1b shows the PVA-coated iron oxides heated at 200°C and 300°C. These results clearly show that the iron oxide particles are crystalline. We can also see that as the temperature increases from 200°C to 300°C the crystallinity is increased and the PVA amorphous back ground is decreased. These results are consistency with our previous results [13]. The heat treatment of 200°C for 24 hrs may not be sufficient to decompose the excess PVA, as this temperature is well below the degradation of PVA. PVA-coated Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles that were heated to 300°C for 3 hrs, are more crystalline the and the sample heated at 200°C. All major diffraction peaks in both coated and uncoated samples matches well with magnetite.

Figure 1. Powdered XRD pattern of as prepared a) uncoated Fe_3O_4 b) PVA-coated Fe_3O_4

Magnetization

Magnetization studies were conducted to determine the magnetic saturation as well as the magnetic nature of the iron nanoparticles at room temperature. As seen in Figure 2, all the particles clearly exhibited SPM behavior, with the magnetic saturation reached at room temperature and magnetization decreasing to zero when the applied field is removed. In table 1, uncoated iron oxide was found to reach the highest magnetic saturation of about 61emu/g. With the addition of the PVA coating, there is a significant drop in M_s , most likely due to the polymer presence. It is noted that changing the heating from 200°C for 24 hrs to 300°C for 3 hrs, with the PVA addition, it is sufficient enough to double the magnetization at saturation. It was expected that a polymer coating would decrease the magnetization, here, it is decrease by half. Other polymers may be able to provide the same coverage and dispersion without as much of an adverse effect.

Figure 2. Magnetic curves of as prepared uncoated Fe_3O_4 and PVA-coated Fe_3O_4

Table 1. Magnetic properties of as prepared coated and uncoated Fe_3O_4 .

<i>Sample</i>	H_c (Oe)	M_r (μemu)	M_s (emu/g)
Uncoated	4.22	198.3	60.17
PVA-coated200	21.49	120.6	12.51
PVA-coated300	9.916	194.6	31.32

TEM

TEM analysis was conducted to understand the morphology, surface coatings, and amorphous or crystalline nature of the particles. TEM analysis of both the PVA-coated and uncoated Fe_3O_4 shows the particles are crystalline and spherical in shape. Figure 3a and 3b represents the TEM micrographs of the uncoated Fe_3O_4 particles. The micrograph clearly shows that the particles are uniform in size with minimum agglomeration and the diameter of $\sim 10\text{nm}$. Figure 3c and 3d depicts the TEM micrograph of as-prepared PVA-coated iron oxides. The micrographs clearly show the iron oxide nanoparticles are uniformly coated and mono dispersed with little to no agglomeration. The particle sizes, measured from the micrographs are $\sim 5\text{-}10\text{nm}$. Most importantly, the particle sizes observed in both samples fall within the critical limits for drug delivery applications and are small enough to allow for size increase due to additional coatings or drug loading without reaching above the limits. The PVA-coated particles seem to be completely embedded in the PVA, thereby providing an environment for drug loading, protection from potential oxidation encountered once *in vivo*, and yielding a much more biocompatible material.

Figure 3. TEM micrographs of as prepared (a) and b) uncoated Fe_3O_4 and (c) and d) PVA-coated magnetite

FTIR

FTIR analysis was carried out to determine the presence of the Pluronic-127 and oleic acid coatings on the surface of the iron oxide nanoparticles. Figure 4 depicts the FTIR spectra of a) neat Pluronic-127, b) oleic acid, and c) the surface coated iron oxides. The Figure 4 (b) spectra clearly show the presence of oleic acid on the surface of iron oxide. Clearly defined peaks at 2860, 2919, and 1702 cm^{-1} that are associated with the -CH₂-symmetric, -CH₂- asymmetric, and CO bonds respectively in oleic acid are also present in the coated oxides at similar shifts. The peaks linked to the Pluronic-127 are not as distinct as those associated with the oleic acid, but are present. The broad peak found from the coated oxides located around 984-1070 cm^{-1} is not present in either of the neat surfactants; however there is a combination of several peaks near this range found in oleic acid and Pluronic-127. This peak is most likely the result of combined peaks found at 960 and 1097 cm^{-1} from Pluronic-127 and 914 cm^{-1} from oleic acid.

Figure 4. FTIR spectra of a) Pluronic-127 b) Oleic acid and c) Pluronic-127/oleic acid coated iron oxide

Table 2. Decomposition temperature from TGA curves of oleic acid, Pluronic-127, and Pluronic-127/oleic acid coated oxides.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>T_{decomp} (°C)</i>
Oleic acid	266
Pluronic-127	387
Coated oxides	228, 363

TGA

TGA was also conducted to verify the weight percentage of Pluronic-127 and oleic acid on the iron oxides surface through analysis of the weight loss with respect to temperature. Neat oleic acid was found to have major weight losses around 200-400°C, with less than 10 wt% remaining above 300°C. Pluronic-127 mass loss increased over a single temperature range, peaking at 387°C. The coated iron oxides were found to have two major weight loss steps occurring around 228 and 363°C. There is a definite two step decomposition that occurs in the coated oxide particles due to the presence of both surfactants. The oleic acid decomposes initially, followed by the Pluronic-127. The further studies on this are under investigation.

Figure 5. TGA curve of Pluronic-127/oleic acid coated iron oxide

CONCLUSIONS

Uncoated and PVA-coated Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were prepared using simple one-step synthesis followed by heat treatments. This sonochemical method provides a simple technique to produce both coated and uncoated iron oxide nanoparticles that are of uniform size, shape, and crystallinity. The polymer presence does decrease the magnetic susceptibility; however it increases the biocompatibility and provides an environment for drug loading. The further studies on magnetic properties of Oleic acid, Pluronic-127 and combination of both with drug loading are under investigation.

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